

Post-Permian Folding and Fracturing of the Spraberry and San Andres Formations Within the Midland Basin Region of West Texas

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ABSTRACT

Many major Permian oil and gas fields in West Texas produce from unfaulted anticlines and domes. Published studies commonly explain the folds as products of differential compaction or drape over paleotopography. Data from two of these fields, Spraberry Trend Area and Wasson, suggests that the folds formed by post-Guadalupian epirogenic uplift.

The Spraberry Trend Area field produces from Leonardian deep-water sandstones and siltstones deposited in the Midland Basin. In southwestern Upton County, the Spraberry has been folded into a series of plunging anticlines and monoclines with structural relief up to 400 ft. The folds occur along the margins of a large block of lower Paleozoic rocks. There is no evidence of thinning associated with differential compaction. Restoration of the Spraberry to the original depositional surface suggests that the lower Paleozoic faults were reactivated after Guadalupian time. This basement-involved uplift apparently produced forced folds in the Permian section. The Spraberry has a regional set of northeast trending fractures. The fractures occur in both folded and unfolded areas so they appear to have formed in response to a regional compressive event.

The Wasson San Andres field produces from Guadalupian ramp dolomites deposited on the Northwestern Shelf of the Midland Basin. The structural crest of Wasson is a dome with over 300 ft of closure. The carbonate lithofacies indicate that there was no depositional high in the vicinity of the present dome during San Andres time. There is thinning associated with differential compaction but it occurs over the dome. Structural closure would be even greater if the rocks had not differentially compacted. Therefore, compaction cannot have produced the dome. The domal geometry appears to be the result

of basement-involved uplift of a lower Permian carbonate buildup. The San Andres dolomites are also fractured at Wasson. There is no orientation data at Wasson but northeast-trending San Andres fractures have been reported elsewhere.

There is no data to precisely date the timing of these uplifts. However, the northeast-trending fractures could have formed in response to northeasterly-directed Laramide compression during the Eocene. The structural style of the folds also indicates north-east-directed compressional deformation. Therefore, it is logical to correlate the folding and fracturing with the Laramide deformation because it represents the only post-Guadalupian regional compressive tectonic event in West Texas.

INTRODUCTION

The effects of the Mississippian through early-Wolfcampian Marathon orogeny in the Permian Basin (Hills, 1970, 1985; Ewing, 1991) are well-documented. However, post-Wolfcampian rocks have been folded into anticlines, domes and monoclines in many parts of the Permian basin region (Figure 1). These structural features are subtle but highly significant because they are partly responsible for trapping hydrocarbons in several major fields.

Many authors explain these folds as the products of differential compaction and/or draping of paleotopography (Wessel, 1992; Dull, 1992; Purves, 1990; Chuber and Pusey, 1985). Study of the geometries of the structures suggests that forced folding above reactivated fault blocks is a more plausible mechanism. This alternative requires a post-Wolfcampian tectonic event within the Permian Basin. The early Tertiary Laramide phase of the Cordilleran Orogeny (Drewes, 1991) is the logical candidate for this event. The Permian Basin region was

Figure 1- Folds involving Leonardian and younger rocks of the Permian Basin. W = Wasson field, S = Seminole Field, M = Mabee field, HG = Howard-Glasscock field, GEL = Giddings Estate Lease, PU = Pembroke Unit, Y = Yates field, BM = Barrilla Mountains (modified from Winfree, 1992).

part of the Cordilleran foreland during the Eocene. Horak (1985) and Winfree (1992) have postulated that epeirogenic deformation occurred in the Midland Basin as a result of Laramide compression.

The main purpose of the paper is to document post-Permian folding and fracturing within the Midland Basin region by describing examples from the Leonardian Spraberry Formation and the Guadalupian San Andres Formation (Figure 2). There is no direct evidence to positively link this deformation to the Laramide orogeny but there is a compelling body of circumstantial evidence that provides a basis to propose that there is a direct relationship. This will remain only a hypothesis, however, until further evidence can be gathered. The author hopes that this paper will stimulate discussion that will lead to more research on this topic.

MESOZOIC AND CENOZOIC TECTONICS OF THE PERMIAN BASIN

Mesozoic Rifting

The Mesozoic rifting that created the Gulf of Mexico and Chihuahua Trough apparently affected areas adjacent to the Permian Basin (Ewing, 1991, 1993; Dickerson, 1985). No related faulting is known within the Permian Basin but the eastern, southern, and western margins were subjected to pre-Cretaceous uplift and erosion (Ewing, 1993) which resulted in the removal of Permian rocks below the basal Cretaceous (Albian) unconformity.

Laramide Compression

CRETACEOUS	TRINITY, FREDRICKSBURG, AND WASHITA GROUPS
TRIASSIC	DOCKUM GROUP
OCHOAN	DEWEY LAKE RUSTLER SALADO
GUADALUPIAN	TANSILL YATES SEVEN RIVERS QUEEN GRAYBURG SAN ANDRES
LEONARDIAN	CLEARFORK (SHELVES) SPRABERRY (BASIN) WITCHITA (SHELVES)

Figure 2- Generalized post-Wolfcampian stratigraphic chart.

The Cordilleran Orogeny affected the western margin of North America from the late Jurassic through the early Tertiary. Apparently, the deformation migrated eastward with time in response to convergence of plates caught between the mid-Pacific and mid-Atlantic spreading centers. These opposing plate motions produced northeast-directed compression over a very large area (Drewes, 1991; Price and Henry, 1984; 1985).

Northeast-directed compression had migrated into West Texas by the close of the Cretaceous during the Laramide phase of the Cordilleran Orogeny (Drewes, 1991). Over the decades since J. D. Dana (1895) introduced the term Laramide, it has been widely applied to many late Cretaceous-early Tertiary deformational events throughout western North America. Therefore the term is too vague to be locally useful without further definition (Stevens and Stevens, 1990, Tweto, 1975).

Several workers have described the effects of the Laramide compression in West Texas and New Mexico (Ewing, 1991; Muehlberger and Dickerson, 1989; Seager and Mack, 1986; Calhoun and Webster, 1983; Kelley; 1971). These studies define the Laramide structural style that is relevant to the Permian Basin region. Key elements of that style include high-angle reverse faults, strike-slip faults, monoclines and broad anticlines and synclines. Many of these structures appear to be localized along older Paleozoic zones of weakness and, in many cases, pre-existing faults have been reactivated. There are two, slightly different orientations of the principal compressive stress. Early Laramide compression was directed N50-55E and later it changed to N65-80E (Price and Henry, 1984).

Dramatic examples of Laramide deformation are not known from the interior of the Permian Basin but they occur on the western and southern margins (Kelley, 1971; Calhoun and Webster, 1983). One important example is the Carta Valley Fault Zone (Webster, 1980) of Edwards and Kinney counties of Texas (Figure 3). Cretaceous rocks on the surface have been broken by a series of northeast-trending faults that form a set of *en echelon* grabens. These are apparently related to left-lateral movement on a deeper-seated, pre-Cretaceous fault zone bounding the Devils River Uplift (Calhoun and Webster, 1983). The Carta Valley Fault Zone is a significant example because similar reactivated fault zones probably occur in the Midland Basin, where the degree of defor-

Figure 3- A) Surface geology of the Carta Valley Fault Zone (from Webster, 1980). B) Interpreted origin of Carta Valley Fault Zone in response to Laramide compression (from Calhoun and Webster, 1983).

mation is expected to be much less.

Post-Laramide Extension

Laramide compression had waned by about 30 m.y. ago and West Texas began to experience east-northeast extension (Price and Henry, 1984; 1985; Ewing, 1991). Dikes emplaced throughout the Trans-Pecos region before 30 m.y. ago record the waning northeast-directed compression of the Laramide (Price and Henry, 1984). Calzia and Hiss (1978) describe northeast-trending dikes within the northern Delaware Basin with apparent ages ranging from 30-34 m.y. If these intrusives were emplaced under the early Basin and Range stress regime, they would have northwesterly orientations. Therefore, parts of the Permian Basin must have been under compression at that time also.

By about 10 m.y. ago, the direction of maximum extension shifted to the northwest. This event affected the western margins of the Permian Basin along the Delaware/Guadalupe Mountains trend (Collins and Raney, 1994; Goertz, 1985; Hentz and Henry, 1989). Hentz and Henry (1989) maintain that late Tertiary extension produced the northeast-trending grabens and fractures that control the sulfur deposits of the western Delaware Basin. Seismicity contin-

ues today in the Trans-Pecos and it appears to be related to right-lateral transtension (Dumas, 1980; Ewing, 1991).

Stevens and Stevens (1990) have shown that localized areas of post-Laramide compressive deformation occurred in Trans-Pecos Texas during a regional episode of large-scale right-lateral transtension. No compressional structures of this age have been documented in the Permian Basin but folded Oligocene volcanic rocks occur along the southwestern margin of the Delaware Basin in the Barrilla Mountains (Eifler, 1951; Pearson, 1985).

FOLDING AND FRACTURING OF THE SPRABERRY

Background

The Spraberry was named for the A.J. Spraberry lease in Dawson County, Texas in the area that later became the Spraberry field (McLennan and Bradley, 1951). Production was established in 1949 at several different sites in the Midland Basin. Over 2000 wells were drilled in the next three years and the individual fields were consolidated into the Spraberry Trend Area field (Figure 4).

The Spraberry is a deep water clastic deposit (Sil-

Figure 4- Index map of Spraberry study areas.

SUMMARY OF SPRABERRY FRACTURE ORIENTATION DATA

Figure 5- Published fracture orientation data from the Spraberry Trend Area field (from Elkins and Skov, 1960).

Figure 6- Regional structure of the Spraberry Trend Area field (from Wilkinson, 1953).

ver and Todd, 1969; Handford, 1981; Tyler and Gholston, 1988). Throughout the southern part of the Midland Basin, the reservoir consists of two sandstone pay intervals separated by about 900 ft of organic-rich siltstone with minor sandstone.

Natural Fractures in the Spraberry

Typical matrix permeabilities measured in Spraberry sandstone cores are less than 0.5 md. However, pressure data published by Dyes and Johnston (1953) indicates that effective permeabilities range from 2 to 183 md. The effective permeability is provided by a network of interconnected fractures. Wilkinson (1953) first pointed out that, while the oil was stored primarily in the matrix, fractures provide almost all of the permeability. Reservoir engineering studies during the mid-to-late 1950s confirmed this conclusion (Aguilera, 1980). Elkins and Skov (1960) summarized several lines of evidence that indicate a consistent northeast orientation of the fractures (Figure 5). The average orientation is N56E with a range of N36E to N76E. The consistent orientation and widespread distribution of the fractures suggests that they are a regionally parallel set that probably developed in response to a regional-scale compressive stress.

Spraberry Structural Geology

Most of the Spraberry Trend Area field has a homoclinal structure (Figure 6). The homocline dips very gently (less than 1 degree) to the west into the deepest part of the Midland Basin. The axis of the structural basin parallels the Central Basin Platform. The original south depositional dip (Tyler and Gholston, 1988; Tyler et al., 1987); is perpendicular to the homocline so there has been gentle westward tilting of the Midland Basin since the middle Leonardian.

Post-Leonardian folds have been superimposed on the homocline in the southern part of the Spraberry Trend (Figure 6). There is a dome over the Benedum Ellenburger field that plunges northwestward to form a large nose; here referred to as the Benedum-Pembrook nose (Figure 7). The Giddings monocline (Figure 7) extends westward across the Giddings Estate lease from the northern end of the Benedum-Pembrook nose. There is a small, low-relief dome superimposed on the monocline above the Immelman

Ellenburger/Fusselman field.

The Benedum-Pembrook and Giddings folds overlie a large fault-bounded block of lower Paleozoic rocks (Figure 8). The Giddings monocline overlies a down-to-the-north fault zone that forms the northern boundary. This fault zone is marked on the surface by High Lonesome Draw so the block will be referred to as the HLD block in this paper. The Benedum-Pembrook nose marks the northeast boundary of the block. It overlies a down-to-the-northeast zone of reverse faults that cut as high as the lower Wolfcamp. There is a down-to-the-north fault zone along the southern boundary that cuts the north end of Benedum and the south end of the Amacker-Tippett Ellenburger field. It is roughly parallel to the Giddings fault zone and it is also overlain by a north-facing monocline. The western margin of the block consists of a down-to-the-west fault zone on the west side of the Wilshire and Amacker-Tippett fields. This western boundary fault zone is overlain by an anticline in the Spraberry.

Proposed Origin of Spraberry Folds

Stearns (1978) provides the following definition that is useful here: "A forced fold is one in which the overall shape and trend are dominated by the irregular shape of some forcing member below." I propose that the HLD block was uplifted sometime after Spraberry deposition and that the uplift produced forced folds in the unfaulted section.

Detailed correlations between closely-spaced wells on the Giddings Estate lease help constrain the timing of structural growth. The lowermost Spraberry sand pinches out from north to south across the Giddings monocline apparently in response to about 5 ft of paleotopographic relief. The Spraberry interval thins by about 10 ft across the flexure. This is about 1% of the total interval. These numbers indicate that the HLD block was rising relative to the rest of the Midland Basin but only by a small amount. The small amount of thinning strongly suggests that almost all of the growth of this feature occurred in post-Spraberry time. In fact, there is similar structural closure at least as high as the Grayburg along this trend (Figure 9). There is no evidence of thinning in the Spraberry-to-Grayburg interval that suggests that differential compaction could be a significant factor.

As a basinal deposit, the original top of the Spraberry was a surface with extremely low dip. In

Figure 7- Structure of the top of the Spraberry in the Giddings Estate Lease and Pembroke Unit areas (modified from Winfree, 1992). Cross section E-W is figure 8.

Figure 8- Boundaries of the HLD block in Upton County. Dashed arrows represent Spraberry structure. Heavy lines represent fault zones bounding the block. Cross section E-W is figure 8.

GIDDINGS-PEMBROOK SPRABERRY STRUCTURAL CROSS SECTION

STRUCTURAL RESTORATION AT END OF SPRABERRY DEPOSITION

Figure 9- Schematic cross section across the northeastern corner of the HLD block. Structure of the faulted section is highly generalized. Eight wells were used to construct the section. For the restoration, the top of the Spraberry surface in each well was lowered to match the deepest well which is the one at the far left. Vertical exaggeration is only about 1.5X. Location of cross section is shown in figures 6 and 7.

Figure 9, the Spraberry has been restored to an unfolded geometry. At the end of Spraberry deposition, the underlying fault zones had significantly less throw than they do now. The current structural relief across the fault zones bounding the HLD block requires the addition of approximately 200 ft of throw after Spraberry time. It is therefore reasonable to conclude that most of the present structural relief of the Leonardian and Guadalupian sections occurred in the post-Permian by forced folding.

The structural styles of the forced folds are consistent with uplift in response to northeast-directed compression. The anticlinal noses and domes overlying the east and west boundaries of the HLD block formed as north-northwest-trending faults were reactivated at right angles to the maximum compressive stress. The monoclines formed over the north and south boundaries where the underlying fault zones were more nearly parallel with the maximum compression. These fault zones probably did not experi-

ence as much compression. The overlying monoclines reflect the uplift of the entire HLD block rather than localized uplift of individual fault sub-blocks. The southern boundary monocline is down to the north so the block south of the HLD block was uplifted more.

Proposed Origin of Spraberry Fractures

Previous studies have suggested that the Spraberry fractures formed by changes in sediment volume, regional extension during subsidence, or to local uplift of anticlines (Gibson, 1951; Wilkinson, 1953). Lorenz et al. (1991) present arguments that show that these mechanisms cannot produce a regional set of parallel fractures. It is tempting to relate the fracturing to the flexure of the rocks during folding. However, there are logical problems with that association. First, the unflexed homoclinal area is fractured. Secondly, the intensity of the flexing is not sufficient to

Figure 10- Top of San Andres main pay porosity, Wasson field, Yoakum County (modified from Ware, 1988). Scale is 3.2 miles per inch. Cross section A-A' is figure 11.

produce much fracturing (J.M. DeGraff, pers. comm., 1990). Furthermore, fractures produced by flexing would not have regionally parallel orientations.

The parallel orientation of the fractures across the entire region suggests that the fractures formed by some large-scale mechanism probably related to regional compression. Lorenz et al. (1991) have proposed a mechanism for fracturing of Cretaceous sands in Colorado that may apply to the Spraberry. Their process depends on an anisotropic stress distribution and elevated pore pressure. Increased pore pressure increases the brittleness of the rock. When a sufficient contrast between the least and maximum stresses occurs, extension perpendicular to the maximum stress direction will begin. This extension produces fractures that parallel the maximum compressive stress.

FOLDING AND FRACTURING OF THE WASSON SAN ANDRES FIELD

Background

The Wasson San Andres field of Gaines and Yoakum counties lies on the Northwestern Shelf of the Midland Basin. It is a structural trap that consists of two northwesterly-trending folds, the Denver Dome and the Roberts Dome, and a northeast-trending nose, the ODC Nose (Figure 10).

The San Andres was first described by Lee and Girty (1909) in the San Andres Mountains in Sierra County, New Mexico. Kottowski et al. (1956) and Lindsay (1994) have provided additional useful detail in the area of the type section. Ramondetta's (1982a, 1982b) regional studies of the San Andres of the Northwestern Shelf establish a useful framework to understand the setting of Wasson.

Proposed Origin of San Andres Folds

Ramondetta's (1982b) regional San Andres structure maps (Figure 11) illustrate the homoclinal nature of large parts of the Northwestern Shelf. The homocline dips about 0.3 degrees on the Pi Marker, a silty dolomite bed that can be correlated all around the Northwestern shelf (it forms a reliable structural marker). In places, the homocline is disrupted by monoclines with dips up to about one degree. The

steepest monocline overlies the Wolfcampian shelf margin with dips up to two degrees. The Wasson Field folds rise above the surrounding homocline and merge with the shelf margin monocline. Dips on the flanks of the dome range from one to two degrees.

The San Andres consists of a series of late Leonardian and early Guadalupian dolomitized carbonate ramps that prograded south into the Midland Basin. The author's detailed description of over 3000 ft of San Andres core in the Exxon-operated Cornell Unit and published studies from other areas of Wasson (Bent, 1992; Mathis, 1986) indicate that the depositional slope had almost no paleotopographic relief. There is no correlation of facies and present-day structure. The Cornell unit lies on the flank of the Denver Dome and present-day structural dip is northerly (Figure 10). Original depositional dip was southeast. Apparently, paleotopography did not contribute to the growth of the folds.

The folds in the Wasson field involve the post-San Andres section at least as high as the Yates sandstone (Figure 12). There is evidence of thinning in the Yates to base of San Andres interval that correlates well with structural elevation (Figure 13) and the Pi marker. Detailed correlations suggest that this thinning is not due to depositional onlap because individual beds appear to correlate across the thinned area. The area of thinning coincides with the crest of the Denver Dome so it seems that differential compaction has occurred over the fold. The effect of this compaction is to reduce the structural relief. If the compaction effects are removed the closure would have even greater height so differential compaction could not have caused the structural relief.

Evidence of compaction is abundant in the Cornell Unit cores. Large stylolites with amplitudes in excess of 5 cm are present and lower-amplitude stylolites typically occur in every foot of the mud-rich facies. Other areas of the Northwestern Shelf do not appear to have undergone as much compaction. Stylolites are rare in Exxon's cores from a correlative interval of the San Andres in the Slaughter-Lelleveland Field (Coons lease, Hockley county, Texas). Published studies from other parts of Slaughter-Lelleveland (Ebanks, 1990; Dulaney and Hadik, 1990) do not report stylolites either. This suggests that the Wasson area may have undergone a greater degree of compaction. Ramondetta's (1982b) regional isopachs show that the Wasson area lies within

Figure 11- Regional structure of the Pi Marker (modified from Ramondetta, 1982b).

NORTH-SOUTH STRUCTURAL CROSS SECTION WASSON FIELD

Figure 12- Schematic cross section of the Guadalupian section of the Wasson field. Six wells were used to construct this section. Location of section in figure 9. Vertical exaggeration is 8.6X.

YATES TO BASE SAN ANDRES THICKNESS VS. PI MARKER ELEVATION

Figure 13- Plot of thickness of the Yates to base of San Andres interval vs. structural elevation. Each point represents one well on the Denver Dome.

Figure 14- Burial history curves for the Permian Basin region (from Horak, 1985).

a regional San Andres thin. The regional thin roughly correlates with the area of the underlying Wolfcampian shelf margin carbonate buildups.

Post-Guadalupian uplift of the Wolfcampian buildups could have produced the area of greater compaction and the forced folds in the San Andres. Horak's (1985) burial history curve (Figure 14) indicates that the Guadalupian section reached maximum burial just before uplift began at the beginning of the Tertiary. If the Wolfcampian buildups were uplifted at that time they would have added increased vertical stress to the overburden stress. Compaction would occur only in those areas of uplift so thinning would correlate with structural highs.

Fracturing of the San Andres

The San Andres is only locally fractured. Most interpretations of San Andres core data (Bebout and Harris, 1990) do not report significant fracturing.

However, fracturing seems to be more common where the San Andres has been folded.

The cores from the Cornell unit contain many natural fractures. There are two types: anhydrite-filled and open. The open fractures are oil-stained and occasionally mineralized. There is no orientation data for these fractures. Orientation data does exist for San Andres fractures at the Vacuum field of Lea County, New Mexico (approximately 35 southwest of Wasson). Purves (1990) reported orientations of N60E and N65E for the interval from 1000 ft to 9000 ft which includes the San Andres. There is significant folding of the San Andres in the Vacuum field. Chuber and Pusey (1985) report San Andres fractures from the Reeves Field, which produces from folded San Andres rocks just southeast of Wasson Field.

It seems likely that the areas of uplift that produced forced folding and compaction in the San Andres may have been areas of elevated pore pres-

Figure 15- A) San Andres structure of the Yates field. B) Top of Cretaceous Trinity sandstone at Yates (from Berger et al, 1992).

Figure 16- Structural cross section of San Andres pay at the Mabee field of Andrews and Martin counties (from Horvath and Miller, 1994). Note folding of originally flat supratidal layer at the top of zone 1.

sure. These localized areas may have been susceptible to fracturing in response to Laramide compression. Additional orientation data could test this hypothesis.

OTHER AREAS OF POSSIBLE POST-GUADALUPIAN FORCED FOLDING

Brief inspection of published maps and cross-sections suggests that many other producing fields in the Midland Basin area experienced post-Guadalupean forced folding. Detailed study of thickness relationships and depositional facies of these fields is beyond the scope of this study so these examples must be considered speculative.

The Yates field in Pecos County, Texas is a possible example of a Laramide fold (Figure 15). This dome has about 150 ft of closure (Berger, 1992; Wessel, 1992) at the surface where the Cretaceous crops out. The closure extends at least as deep as the San Andres and is parallel with the surface expression at that depth. The greater relief at the San Andres level suggests that some differential compaction over the dome occurred between the Guadalupean and Cretaceous. As mentioned above, restoration of pre-compaction thicknesses would increase the structural relief, so folding as a result of differential compaction seems unlikely. Wessel (1992) stated that the dip on the flanks of the Yates dome "is likely a function of original dip and diagenesis of underlying strata ... locally enhanced by the dissolution of halite in the Salado Formation near the perimeter of the field." Wessel presents no detailed data to support the diagenetic argument so no judgment can be made about the impact of that process. Paleotopography is a doubtful contributor to structural relief. Any paleotopography on the San Andres depositional surface was probably an order of magnitude less than the present-day structural closure. The mechanisms that Wessel lists certainly occurred at Yates but they are not significant enough to explain the structural relief of the Cretaceous dome.

There are several other San Andres traps that appear to be controlled, at least in part, by forced folds. Two are worth mentioning here. Horvath and Miller (1994) published a cross section (Figure 16) from the Mabee San Andres field that clearly shows post-depositional folding. The facies relationships indicate that the originally very low-angle depositional surfaces have been folded into a series of anticlines

and synclines.

The Howard-Glasscock field (Figure 1) is another possible post-Guadalupean forced fold that produces from the San Andres. It is significant for two reasons. First, if it is a forced fold, its location on the Eastern Shelf margin would indicate that uplift occurred across the entire width of the Midland Basin. Second, Howard-Glasscock is at the eastern end of an aligned trend of low-relief folds that produce from the San Andres or Grayburg sections. This trend extends westward from Howard-Glasscock across Glasscock County into Midland County to include the McDowell, Zant, Germania, Azalea, and Brazos Fields. Such a structural alignment suggests that a large-scale deeper zone of weakness was re-activated in post-Guadalupean time.

The regional distribution of folds in the post-Wolfcampian section (Figure 1) suggests that many of the large structural blocks of the Central Basin Platform were uplifted in post-Guadalupean time. Gardiner (1990) and Shumaker (1992) have described the major fault-bounded blocks of the Central Basin Platform. There is a significant Yates monocline overlying the northeastern margin of the Fort Stockton and Sand Hills blocks of Gardiner (1990). Another monocline overlies the Wolfcampian shelf margin on the east side of the Platform in Upton, Crane, and Ector counties. Longacre (1990) reports faults that cut the Grayburg along this trend. This monocline continues into Andrews County where it overlies a major northwest-trending fault zone. Both of these monoclines dip to the northeast. If they are forced folds, they indicate uplift of the blocks to the southwest. The fault zone that bounds the western margin of the Platform is overlain by a Yates anticline that extends from Pecos County to central Lea County. This feature could be a fault bend fold formed by post-Guadalupean reactivation of the underlying faults. The entire Central Basin Platform could have been reactivated as a foreland basement uplift as a result of Laramide compression. While it has less structural relief and a smaller areal extent than most Laramide uplifts of the Wyoming foreland, it does have the same structural style in the post-Wolfcampian section.

DISCUSSION

The evidence presented above strongly suggests that regional fracturing and epeirogenic folding oc-

curred after deposition of the Leonardian and Guadalupian rocks within the Permian Basin. It is not presently possible to precisely constrain the timing of this deformation. The association of forced folding with a regional set of northeast-trending fractures is consistent with Laramide foreland deformation during the Eocene. Alternate hypotheses also have merit, though, because there is no direct evidence to prove that the folding and fracturing occurred at the same time. Two alternate hypotheses will be presented that treat the folding and fracturing as independent deformational events. The preferred hypothesis is presented after the alternatives.

Mesozoic Folding Followed by Laramide Fracturing

The first alternate hypothesis is that the folds are pre-Cretaceous and that the fracturing was caused by Laramide compression. It is possible that the documented Mesozoic uplift around the margins of the Permian Basin (Ewing, 1993) produced the post-Guadalupian folds by reactivation of existing fault blocks. This explanation would be consistent with the geometry of the monoclines of the HLD block. However, the Mesozoic tectonics appear to be basically extensional so one would not expect the anticlinal folds unless the underlying fault blocks had been rotated. Furthermore, the effects of the Mesozoic uplift appear to die out northward. The Upton County folds may have been influenced by pre-Albian uplift but the folds of the Northwestern Shelf would appear to be unrelated because of their distance from known areas of uplift. Post-Cretaceous folding in Pecos County would still be required to explain the Cretaceous dome at the Yates field if it is a forced fold.

The argument for Laramide fracturing is presented below. It would be unchanged in this hypothesis except that the development of localized areas of fractured San Andres would remain unexplained.

Late Tertiary Folding and Fracturing

The second alternate hypothesis is that post-Laramide deformation related to the Basin and Range extension produced both the folds and the fractures. The effects of this event on the western margin of the Permian Basin are well-documented (Goertz, 1985; King, 1948). Hentz (1990) describes northeast-trending fractures and grabens formed during the

Miocene through Recent episode of northwesterly-directed extension. It is possible that the Spraberry and San Andres fractures could have formed in this same stress field. However, this hypothesis will not explain why the San Andres is unfractured in most areas.

Stevens and Stevens (1990) have described compressional folding in the Big Bend region within a regional setting of right-lateral transtension from the end of the Cretaceous through the Oligocene. The compressional features occur where margins of blocks were crowded together by rotation of the entire block. Extensional features formed at the block margins where rotation produced separation between the blocks. It is possible that the Spraberry and San Andres folds formed in a similar manner but the lack of extensional structures along the HLD block margins suggests otherwise. While the HLD block may have undergone slight rotation, it was probably transpressive in nature. It is hard to imagine that the large Yates anticline along the western margin of the Central Basin Platform could have formed as a result of rotation in an extensional stress regime.

Preferred Hypothesis: Laramide Folding and Fracturing

The preferred hypothesis is that the folding and fracturing were roughly contemporaneous and that both are the products of Laramide compression. Pre-Laramide uplift may have contributed some structural relief in the southern part of the Midland Basin area and post-Laramide extensional stresses may have acted to keep the fractures open but these effects are probably minor.

The Laramide hypothesis rests on three points. First, pore pressure was probably elevated in the early Tertiary so the conditions were right to form a regional set of fractures parallel to the Laramide principle compressive stress. Second, the folds appear to have been formed by compressional uplift of fault-bounded basement blocks. Third, circumstantial evidence suggests that the two deformational events occurred simultaneously.

Evidence for Elevated Pore Pressure and Fracturing in the Early Tertiary:

There is indirect evidence that early Cenozoic fracturing could have occurred in the Midland Basin.

Horak (1985) indicates that maximum burial occurred during the latest Cretaceous (Figure 14). The combination of maximum burial and a northeast-oriented compressive stress could have produced the regional set of fractures in the Spraberry and localized areas of fractured San Andres rocks in the same manner as that postulated for Laramide fractures in Colorado by Lorenz et al. (1991).

Geochemical evidence exists to support increased pore pressure within the Spraberry during the late-Cretaceous/early Tertiary burial. Dow et al. (1990) studied source rocks and oils at Pegasus field in Midland county. They concluded that the pre-Permian rocks there reached peak oil generation in the early to middle Mesozoic. The Permian source rocks are currently at the peak generation state. Given that uplift has occurred since the early Tertiary (Horak, 1985), one might conclude that peak generation and associated higher pore pressure coincided with the beginning of Laramide uplift.

There is much less data on the fractures within the San Andres. If elevated pore pressure existed in the San Andres, it was probably localized where uplift was sufficient to produce forced folding. At the time of uplift, the San Andres would have been under maximum overburden. The addition of vertical stress during uplift could have raised pore pressure enough to allow fractures to form parallel to the Laramide principle stress direction on local structural highs.

Evidence for Forced Folding:

The chief argument for Laramide folding within the Permian Basin is that post-Guadalupean folds appear to be formed by forced folding due to uplift of basement-involved fault blocks. The relatively constant thicknesses of the folded Leonardian and Guadalupean sections is inconsistent with folding as a result of differential compaction or draping of topography. Where the sections do thin, differential compaction has apparently occurred but the thinning is minor compared to the structural relief of the folds. Furthermore, the thinning occurs on the crest of the folds which is also inconsistent with a completely passive style of folding. If the rocks were not compacted over the fold, the structural relief would be even greater.

The association of deeper fault blocks and the post-Guadalupean folds, suggest a genetic relationship.

The presence of anticlines over fault zones normal to the Laramide compressive stress and monoclines over the parallel fault zones argue for compressional uplift in Upton County. This argument is strengthened by the fact that Spraberry depositional surfaces must have been very low angle. Uplift of the underlying fault blocks is required to produce the present Spraberry structure. Likewise, the facies of the San Andres at Wasson indicate that uplift of the underlying section has occurred. Therefore, forced folding seems to be the best explanation.

Circumstantial Evidence to Constrain Timing of Deformation:

The argument for contemporaneous folding and fracturing is made here because compression apparently formed both the fractures and the folds and the Laramide is the only documented post-Permian regional episode of compression that affected the Midland Basin. The existence of 30 m.y. old igneous dikes with northeast orientations in the Delaware Basin (Calzia and Hiss, 1978) suggest that compression did continue past the time of maximum burial. Contemporaneous folding and fracturing at the time of maximum burial is the best way to explain why the San Andres is only fractured where it is folded.

ECONOMIC SIGNIFICANCE

The imprint of post-Guadalupean compressive stresses in the Midland Basin region has economically significant implications. This is true not only of the Spraberry and San Andres but of many other important plays. If the fracturing extends to the surface in some areas, there may be important implications for groundwater as well.

Areas of Greater Fracture Intensity Within the Spraberry

Greater fracture intensity may occur in predictable areas within the Spraberry Trend Area field. The Carta Valley fault zone may be considered as a model for a localized area of greater fracture intensity that formed by Laramide reactivation of a deeper fault block. The Carta Valley fault zone was created when the Devils River Uplift was pushed eastward during the Laramide (Webster, 1980; Calhoun and Webster, 1983) causing left-lateral movement along the east-

Figure 17- Maximum average barrels oil per day of Giddings Estate Spraberry wells. Representation of High Lonesome Fault Zone is highly generalized. Detailed mapping indicates that this zone consists of dozens of intersecting faults.

west trending fault that bounds the northern margin of the Uplift (Figure 3). This motion produced an *en echelon* set of northeast-trending grabens, creating a large diffused fracture zone.

It is likely that small amounts of left-lateral motion occurred along some pre-existing east-west trending fault zones within the Midland Basin. This could produce additional northeast-trending fractures in a narrow band above the fault zone. Initial average production rates for the Giddings Estate Spraberry wells along the northern fault zone of the HLD block are higher than those north and south of the zone (Figure 17). This pattern of increased initial productivity does not correlate with the net reservoir thicknesses or cumulative production so it is reasonable to conclude that the Spraberry has a greater fracture intensity above that fault zone. Similar zones probably exist elsewhere in the Spraberry Trend Area.

Areas above major east-west trending fault zones

will probably need to be managed differently than other parts of the field. If these areas have not been waterflooded, they may be highly prospective. If such areas have been waterflooded for many years, they may have been thoroughly swept and infill drilling may be unsuccessful. In areas of intermediate waterflooding, greater fracture intensity could have led to premature breakthrough and bypassing of significant reserves.

Exploration for Small San Andres Fields

The trend of small San Andres fields extending west from Howard-Glasscock mentioned above may not be unique. The GMK-Cedar Lake trend of Gaines County is probably another example. The major barrier to exploration of these small fields is the difficulty of accurately imaging low-relief San Andres structures coupled with the low average per-well re-

coveries. These fields can be profitable, however, if dry holes are minimized both in exploration and development. Acquisition of 3D seismic could be targeted to exploit these trends and to reduce dry hole risk.

Correspondence of San Andres Folds and Fractures: Implications for Clearfork Fields

Most published studies concerning the management of San Andres fields (Bebout and Harris, 1990) do not emphasize the role of fractures. This is partly due to a lack of significant fractures in many San Andres fields and partly due to a lack of data. If the uplift that folded the San Andres also provided the extra stress to produce the fractures then one must ask if every fold within the San Andres is also fractured. Obviously, there must be a minimum threshold depth of burial before uplift could cause the fractures. Therefore some folded San Andres rocks probably remain unfractured. Even where the San Andres has been folded but not fractured, it seems reasonable to expect that the deeper Clearfork section would

be fractured. The implications for flooding and infill drilling are the same as those mentioned above for the Spraberry.

Implications for Pre-Leonardian Structural Plays

There are several implications for the pre-Leonardian plays if pre-existing fault blocks have been reactivated. One must question the effectiveness of fault seal where significant post-Permian uplift has occurred. North or northwest-trending faults may have effective seals but east-west trending faults probably would not. It is not known if areas of greater fracturing occur along the reactivated fault zones in the pre-Leonardian section but it certainly possible.

If the presence of a Post-Permian fold indicates uplift of the underlying section, then the geometry of the fold probably provides useful information about deeper prospects. The anticlinal fold over the San Andres at Seminole field is a direct reflection of the underlying topography of the Wolfcampian and Leonardian carbonate buildups (Figure 18). The crest

DIAGRAMMATIC STRUCTURE OF THE SEMINOLE FIELD

Figure 18- Schematic representation of the Seminole field producing horizons. No scale. No wells were used in constructing this diagram but the geometries are based on mapping done by the author and other Exxon geologists.

of the buildup underlies the crest of the San Andres high. However, the Seminole Deep "Devonian" field is a small anticline that lies along the axis of the San Andres fold but significantly downdip from the crest. Apparently, the post-Permian uplift did not reactivate every deeper fault equally. Certain fault blocks could be uplifted higher but be non-prospective because they lack fault-independent closure. The blocks with fault-independent closure could produce from lower elevations or from the down sides of major reactivated faults. These observations suggest two things. First, each San Andres high is probably prospective in deeper zones if reservoir and seal are present, because of the parallel nature of the folding. Second, deeper exploration should not be limited to the crest of the San Andres fold. Small but commercially attractive prospects may be present that are not reflected in the shallow structure.

Possibilities for New Fractured Plays

The reactivation of the fault zones in post-Permian time creates a complex pattern of deformation in the uppermost Pennsylvanian and lower Wolfcampian rocks. Presumably, these rocks were unfaulted or only slightly offset by faults at the close of Wolfcampian time. The reactivation would produce new faulting and relatively intense folding near the fault zone. It is logical to conclude that these rocks may be highly fractured near reactivated fault zones. Throughout most of the Midland Basin, these rocks are highly organic shales that are known to be source rocks. Is it possible that a fractured shale play exists in these areas that has been overlooked? It is hard to imagine that any play has been overlooked in the Midland Basin until one remembers that most deep wells are not drilled into fault zones. They are usually drilled significantly away from the fault zone to test a fault-independent closure. Any dry holes that turned out to be near reactivated fault zones may be worth a second look.

Implications for Ground Water

In many areas of the Midland Basin, surface drainage patterns follow deeper east-west trending fault zones. The surface expressions of the fault zones may be due to localized areas of fractured Cretaceous rocks. High Lonesome Draw in Upton County is the

surface expression of the fault zone that forms the northern boundary of the HLD block. The postulated area of greater fracture intensity in the Spraberry lies along this draw. Any fracturing of the Lower Cretaceous would have to be very slight but it may be sufficient to enhance dissolution of the limestone to produce differential erosion that would create the draw. The Cretaceous is poorly exposed in High Lonesome Draw so no conclusions can be drawn about fractures there.

If east-west trending draws represent areas of near-surface fractures, there could be implications for ground water exploration and protection. Obviously, fractures in the Antlers sand would increase the capacity of water wells. Fractures in the Fredricksburg limestones might provide pathways for dissolution so these areas could have additional thicknesses of permeable rock. Recharge could also be greater in these areas if solution channels connect the surface with the Antlers sand. If higher recharge does occur in these areas, the potential for contamination of the Trinity aquifer could be greater.

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